

PROJECT GOA: ITS IMPACT ON THE LEARNINGS OF SCIENCE IN GRADE VI OF APLAYA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

VIRGIE L. DE LOS SANTOS

virgie.delossantos@g.batstate-u.edu.ph

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3716-0134>

Department of Education, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Classrooms today are full of millennial learners. They are labeled with many names such as “Tech Experts.” Their attitudes toward studies are distinct. Teachers often hear words from them like, “I don’t like reading,” or “I forgot to do my homework.” Millennial learners have different elements of learning. This research challenge pedagogues to connect course content to the current culture and make learning outcomes to its great content. Therefore, the purpose of this study was: (1) identify the learning styles of Grade VI pupils in terms of gender, (2) determine the effectiveness of differentiated instruction in terms of (objectives of the lesson, learner’s interest, and assessment), (3) proposed activities to enhance the knowledge and understanding of the objectives in K to 12 Curriculum. Quantitative and qualitative research design were used. As we compare the results of the evaluation of the Grade Six pupils, they learned more in Science through kinesthetic. Meaning pupils prefer to learn through games. Millennial learners want to process information through movements, manipulative and using fine and gross motor skills. Pupils learn more through the use of Project GOA (Games on Achievers), because it promotes enjoyment among diversity of learners. Based from the findings, it is highly recommended to determine the interest of pupils to obtain higher result during evaluation. It is also essential to establish professional partnership to lay the strongest foundation for pupils to develop their confidence and become dedicated adults. If this so, the knowledge acquired by the pupils will enable them to wear an armor of confidence, a sword of readiness and boots of success.

Keywords: teaching and learning, differentiated instructional materials used in teaching Science, quantitative and qualitative, questionnaire, Philippines